

The Role of Digital Marketing in Mediating the Impact of Covid 19 Epidemic and Intensity of Competition on Business Performance (Case Study: Online Business)

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ABSTRACT:

This research was conducted with the aim of the role of digital marketing in mediating the effect of the Covid-19 epidemic and the intensity of competition on business performance (case study: Online Business). This research is an applied study that was conducted in a descriptive-survey manner. The statistical population of this research is an infinite number of customers of Online Business in Noorabad city, who were selected using Cochran's formula for unlimited communities, 384 people, and finally 450 complete questionnaires were received for analysis, and the standard questionnaire was based on 5 dimensions and 21 questions. It was distributed among them. In order to test the assumptions of structural equation model technique and SPSS and Smart PLS was used. According to the obtained results, it indicates that the understanding of the covid-19 epidemic has a positive and significant effect on financial performance. Perception of the Covid-19 pandemic has a negative and significant impact on non-financial performance. Understanding the epidemic of Covid-19 has a positive and significant impact on digital marketing. The intensity of commercial competition has a positive and significant effect on financial performance. The intensity of commercial competition has a positive and significant effect on non-financial performance. The intensity of business competition has a positive and significant effect on digital marketing. Digital marketing has a positive and significant effect on financial performance. Digital marketing has a positive and significant impact on non-financial performance. Adoption of digital marketing can mediate the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on financial performance. Digital marketing adoption can mediate the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on non-financial performance. Digital marketing adoption can mediate the effect of competition intensity on financial performance. Digital marketing adoption can mediate the effect of competition intensity on non-financial performance.

Keywords: digital marketing, covid 19 pandemic, competition, business performance

Introduction

The presence of the Covid-19 pandemic has had a significant impact on the business performance achievements of small, small and medium enterprises (MSME) in Iran. Businesses in general have a

hard time sustaining themselves, especially if they want to improve their performance. One of the businesses under threat due to the Covid-19 pandemic is the online SME business. Small and medium-sized businesses generally experience a decline in performance. This is because the purchasing power of the market has decreased as many people have been affected by the Covid-19 pandemic. Many employees are out of work and many businesses have gone bankrupt, so that their incomes decrease and ultimately their purchasing power also decreases. The impact of these layoffs has made them look for other job opportunities. One of the opportunities that is seen is online businesses, although the business of small and medium enterprises is declining.

This is what makes the competition more intense as more people are now turning to online businesses. The SME business is still attractive because of their perception that everyone should have their basic needs met in the form of quality service delivery. Even though the intensity of competition is getting tougher, businessmen should be able to prepare emergency strategies to deal with the crisis caused by the Covid-19 pandemic (1). Small and medium enterprises should be able to choose a suitable business strategy to maintain and improve their performance. Overall, online business performance has declined.

Declining business performance has been studied by previous researchers, including (2). Achieving business performance of SMEs in the online SME sector is heavily influenced by increasingly intense competition. Intense industry competition can reduce business performance (3). The results of other researches that are consistent with the results of this study have also been conducted by (4), but there are other research results that show the opposite result, that is, the intensity of competition does not reduce performance (5).

Since there are still conflicting research results on the effect of competition intensity on performance, this research was conducted by adding a mediating variable for digital marketing adoption. The reasons or considerations for including digital marketing variables are: 1) Digital marketing is a new strategy that has emerged due to the development of the digital era (6). 2) There are now some businesses that have started implementing digital marketing as a solution to increase their performance. 3) The external environment, such as competition, of course also has an impact on the adoption of digital marketing because competing companies have started using it. 4) From several studies that show that digital marketing can increase performance (7), (8). Digital marketing is used as a mediating variable in this study, which includes all types of digital marketing, from websites, search engine marketing, social media marketing, online marketing, email marketing, and video marketing. Adopting comprehensive digital marketing is indeed suitable for online business considering that all these digital marketing tools can be implemented in MSMEs in the online business sector.

Finally, what can be said is that in the world of e-commerce, competing companies are only one click away from each other. Therefore, it is vital that businesses learn how to create loyalty in their customers in online markets and seek to institutionalize it in their organization in order to prepare for the return of visitors to their website in the future. On the other hand, despite the increase of Internet users, they do not want to provide their sensitive personal information, because they do not trust e-commerce; But for some reasons, the nature of the online business of Noorabad city has been associated with being electronic, because the products of the online business of Noorabad city are tangible, production and consumption are inseparable, and the need for quick communication with different regions and countries is evident in this industry. One of the important points is the issue of trust and confidence in these online companies, which can be obtained from the results of this research. Due to the differences between online shopping and traditional shopping in terms of services, the customer's evaluation of the quality of services received in e-commerce and traditional markets will also be different. Understanding the quality of services in store websites and the quality of electronic services are key factors in the customer's purchase decision compared to traditional markets. This study aims to investigate and explain the role of digital marketing in mediating the effect of competition intensity on business performance. In addition, the development of a digital marketing model to be applied in MSMEs in the online business sector of Noorabad city in Iran is considered to be the main subject of the present study and this research helps us to answer the

question of what factors the role of digital Is marketing effective in mediating competition intensity on business performance?

Material and Methods

This research is applied in terms of purpose and based on descriptive-correlational nature. The statistical population of the research is an infinite number of customers of online businesses in Noorabad city. Due to the fact that the number of the studied population is unknown, for this reason, Cochran's formula is used for the unlimited population, which is considered with an error rate of 0.05. Finally, the number of sample size is 450 people. Based on the conceptual framework that explains the relationship between each variable, a conceptual framework model is developed as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1-1: Conceptual model of the research

In this research, a questionnaire was used to collect the primary data, which is based on a five-point Likert scale. The questionnaire consists of two parts: the first part includes demographic questions to identify the demographic characteristics of the sample. The second part includes specialized questions. To check the validity of the questionnaire, the content validity method was used. This means that the questionnaire has been studied by a number of experts and professors in the field, and according to their opinions, the necessary adjustments will be applied to the questionnaire. Cronbach's alpha coefficient will be calculated to evaluate the reliability of the questionnaire.

Table (1): Quantification of responses to questions in a five-point Likert scale

Selective option	Very much	Much	medium	low	Very low
Score	5	4	3	2	1

Table (2): The number of questions of research variables

Variable	Number of questions
Financial performance	4 questions
Non-financial performance	4 questions
Understanding the Covid-19 Pandemic	5 questions
Intensity of competition in the industry	4 questions
Adoption of digital marketing	4 questions
Total	21 questions

Cronbach's coefficient of error was used to measure the reliability of the questionnaire, and the results were obtained as follows:

Cronbach's alpha coefficient for all dimensions of questionnaires is more than 0.7. Therefore, the reliability of the questionnaire has been evaluated favorably.

Table (3): Calculation of Cronbach's alpha

Variables	alpha coefficient
Financial performance	0/742
Non-financial performance	0/803
Understanding the Covid-19 Pandemic	0/721
Intensity of competition in the industry	0/756
Adoption of digital marketing	0/816
Total	0/768

Analysis of the obtained data has been done using SPSS and Smart PLS statistical software.

Hypotheses

The main hypothesis

The role of digital marketing in mediating the effect of the Covid-19 epidemic and the intensity of competition has a significant impact on online business performance.

Sub-hypotheses

1. The understanding of the Covid-19 epidemic has a negative and significant impact on financial performance.
2. The perception of the Covid-19 pandemic has a negative and significant impact on non-financial performance.
3. Understanding the Covid-19 pandemic has a positive and significant impact on digital marketing.
4. The intensity of commercial competition has a negative and significant effect on financial performance.
5. The intensity of commercial competition has a negative and significant effect on non-financial performance.
6. The intensity of commercial competition has a positive and significant effect on digital marketing.
7. Digital marketing has a positive and significant effect on financial performance.
8. Digital marketing has a positive and significant effect on non-financial performance.
9. Digital marketing adoption can mediate the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on financial performance.
10. Digital marketing adoption can mediate the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on non-financial performance.
11. Adoption of digital marketing can mediate the effect of competition intensity on financial performance.
12. Adoption of digital marketing can mediate the effect of competition intensity on non-financial performance.

Results

Descriptive Statistics

Gender

The findings of the research indicated that 63.30% of the respondents were male and 36.70% were female.

Age

The research findings show that 17.30% of the respondents were under 30 years old, 27.80% from 30 to 40 years old, 32.00% from 40-50 years old, and 22.90% of the respondents were over 50 years old.

Education

The findings of the research show that people with 17.60% diploma education, 17.30% postgraduate education, 34.00% bachelor's degree and 31.10% graduate education made up the statistical sample size.

Descriptive analysis of research variables

Descriptive analysis of research variables based on central parameters and dispersion parameters for the main factors of the research is presented.

Table (7): Descriptive analysis of research variables

Variables	Number	Average	variation range	Variance	standard deviation	maximum	minimum
Understanding the Covid-19 Pandemic	450	3/941	0/516	0/266	2/400	2/600	5/000
Financial performance	450	3/561	0/515	0/266	2/500	2/250	4/750
Non-financial performance	450	3/824	0/597	0/357	2/500	2/500	5/000
Digital marketing	450	3/468	0/634	0/403	3/250	1/750	5/000
Intensity of commercial competition	450	4/007	0/583	0/340	2/500	2/500	5/000

Source: research findings

Data normality test

For the data normality test, the statistical assumptions are set as follows:

H0: The data distribution of the variables is normal

H1: The data distribution of the variables is not normal

The test results are normal, the data are presented in the table.

Table (8): Normality test of research variables

Variables	Number	crookedness	Elongation	ks	Significance
Understanding the Covid-19 Pandemic	450	-0/320	0/146	2/237	0/000
Financial performance	450	-0/037	-0/483	2/507	0/000
Non-financial performance	450	0/057	-0/562	2/494	0/000
Digital marketing	450	0/048	-0/548	2/139	0/000
Intensity of commercial competition	450	-0/309	-0/398	2/425	0/000

Based on the results of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, in all cases, a significance value smaller than the error level (0.05) has been obtained. Therefore, the data distribution is not normal. Therefore, PLS structural equations are used.

External model of research**Construct validity**

Construct validity examines the relationship between the questions of each construct (hidden variable) and the desired construct. In order to check the model, one must first make sure that the questions are correct. In order to show that the hidden variables have been measured correctly, construct validity has been used. In the first round, it was determined that question number 4 should be removed due to the low factor load. The model was re-implemented and the final results of construct validity are presented in Table No. 9.

Table 9: Summary of the results of the construct validity check based on the external model of the research

Questionnaire questions	operational burden	T
Q01	0.901389	61.513372
Q02	0.930110	78.678272
Q03	0.844668	32.739994
Q04	0.842215	26.397718
Q05	0.841489	35.393211
Q06	0.811989	22.735708
Q07	0.836774	26.572266
Q08	0.870246	32.213471
Q09	0.881894	31.863400
Q10	0.860053	30.627118
Q11	0.904125	31.900049
Q12	0.944874	82.770600
Q13	0.930198	66.841503
Q14	0.888277	40.693769
Q15	0.875667	43.220460
Q16	0.796345	19.996006
Q17	0.835324	23.184448
Q18	0.805001	12.578770
Q19	0.880037	29.071402
Q20	0.814161	15.245212
Q21	0.856975	26.559512

Source: research findings

Convergent validity

It shows how the variables of a structure are aligned with each other.

Table 9: Convergent validity of research constructs

Variables	AVE
Understanding the Covid-19 Pandemic	0/761
Financial performance	0/723
Non-financial performance	0/828
Digital marketing	0/721
Intensity of commercial competition	0/704

Source: research findings

The average variance extracted (AVE) is greater than 0.5, so there is convergent validity.

Composite reliability

To measure the reliability of the research structures presented in Table No. 10, two criteria of composite reliability (CR) and Cronbach's alpha are used.

Table 10, composite reliability

Structure	Composite reliability	Cronbach's alpha
Understanding the Covid-19 Pandemic	0/912	0/871
Financial performance	0/905	0/861
Non-financial performance	0/941	0/921
Digital marketing	0/912	0/872
Intensity of commercial competition	0/950	0/930

Hypothesis testing (internal research model)

The general research model is shown in Figure 1. In this model, which is the output of Smart PLS software, a summary of the results related to the standard factor load of the variables is provided. The t statistic and bootstrapping value to measure the significance of relationships are also shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1: partial least squares technique of the research conceptual model

Figure 2: Conceptual model of the research (value of t statistic with bootstrapping)

After the accuracy of the measurement of the research constructs is ensured, the relationships of these constructs become possible to test the research hypotheses.

The first hypothesis: understanding of the Covid-19 pandemic has a positive and significant effect on financial performance.

The standard factor loading of the impact of understanding of the epidemic of Kovid-19 on financial performance has been obtained as 0.696. Also, the value of t statistic is 10.986, which is greater than the critical value of 1.96. Therefore, we can claim with 95% confidence: the first hypothesis is confirmed.

Second hypothesis: understanding of the Covid-19 pandemic has a negative and significant effect on non-financial performance.

The standard factor loading of the effect of understanding of the epidemic of Kovid-19 on non-financial performance has been obtained as 0.618. Also, the value of t statistic is 10.560, which is greater than the critical value of 1.96. Therefore, it can be claimed with 95% confidence: the second hypothesis is confirmed.

The third hypothesis: Understanding the epidemic of Covid-19 has a positive and significant effect on digital marketing.

The standard factor loading of the impact of the understanding of the Covid-19 pandemic on digital marketing has been obtained as 0.656. Also, the value of t statistic is 10.750, which is greater than the critical value of 1.96. Therefore, it can be claimed with 95% confidence: the third hypothesis is confirmed.

The fourth hypothesis: the intensity of business competition has a positive and significant effect on financial performance.

The standard factor loading of the effect of the intensity of commercial competition on financial performance has been obtained as 0.434. Also, the value of t statistic is 6.735, which is greater than the critical value of 1.96. Therefore, it can be claimed with 95% confidence: Hypothesis 4 is confirmed.

Fifth hypothesis: The intensity of commercial competition has a positive and significant effect on non-financial performance.

The standard factor loading of the effect of the intensity of commercial competition on non-financial performance has been obtained as 0.449. Also, the value of t statistic is 6.213, which is greater than the critical value of 1.96. Therefore, it can be claimed with 95% confidence: Hypothesis 5 is confirmed.

Sixth hypothesis: The intensity of commercial competition has a positive and significant effect on digital marketing.

The standard factor loading of the effect of the intensity of commercial competition on the organization's digital marketing has been obtained as 0.480. Also, the value of t statistic is 6.589, which is greater than the critical value of 1.96. Therefore, it can be claimed with 95% confidence: Hypothesis 6 is confirmed.

Seventh hypothesis: Digital marketing has a positive and significant effect on financial performance. The standard factor of digital marketing impact on financial performance is 0.427. Also, the value of t statistic is 6.135, which is greater than the critical value of 1.96. Therefore, it can be claimed with 95% confidence: Hypothesis 7 is confirmed.

The eighth hypothesis: digital marketing has a positive and significant effect on non-financial performance.

The standard factor loading of digital marketing impact on non-financial performance is 0.478. Also, the value of t statistic is 6.433, which is greater than the critical value of 1.96. Therefore, it can be claimed with 95% confidence: Hypothesis 8 is confirmed.

Examining the mediating role of digital marketing and testing the 9th and 10th hypothesis:

A- The mediating role of digital marketing in the relationship between perception of the covid-19 pandemic on financial performance

It was found that "understanding of the Covid-19 pandemic" has an effect on "financial performance" and "digital marketing", and "digital marketing" is also effective on "financial performance". Therefore, to examine the overall impact of the perception of the Covid-19 epidemic on financial performance, the indirect effect of the perception of the Covid-19 epidemic should also be considered. The total effect of the perception of the epidemic of Covid-19 on financial performance = the direct effect of the perception of the epidemic + the indirect effect of the perception of the epidemic
The direct effect of the understanding of the epidemic on the performance of financial performance = 0.696

Indirect effect = the effect of the understanding of the epidemic on the performance of financial performance × the effect of digital marketing on financial performance → $0.696 \times 0.427 = 0.297$

The total effect of understanding of the Covid-19 pandemic on financial performance = direct effect + indirect effect → $0.696 + 0.297 = 0.993$

Sobel's statistic is used to test the significance of indirect effects caused by a mediating variable.

$$Z_1 = \frac{0.656 \times 0.427}{\sqrt{0.427^2 \cdot 0.08^2 + 0.656^2 \cdot 0.11^2}} = 3.949$$

The value of the test statistic using the Sobel test is greater than the value of 1.96. Therefore, it can be said that the mediating role of digital marketing variable is accepted. And thus, it can be stated with 95% probability that the adoption of digital marketing can mediate the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on financial performance.

B- The mediating role of digital marketing in the relationship between the perception of the covid-19 pandemic and non-financial performance

The direct effect of the understanding of the covid-19 epidemic on non-financial performance = 0.618
Indirect effect = effect of understanding of the covid-19 epidemic and non-financial performance × digital marketing effect on non-financial performance → $0.618 \times 0.478 = 0.295$

The total effect of understanding of the covid-19 pandemic on non-financial performance = direct effect + indirect effect → $0.618 + 0.295 = 0.913$

Sobel test:

$$Z_1 = \frac{0.656 \times 0.478}{\sqrt{0.478^2 \cdot 0.09^2 + 0.656^2 \cdot 0.10^2}} = 4.012$$

The value of the test statistic using the Sobel test is greater than the value of 1.96. Therefore, it can be said that the mediating role of digital marketing variable is accepted. And in this way, it can be said with a probability of 95% that the adoption of digital marketing can mediate the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on non-financial performance. And in this way, the tenth hypothesis is also confirmed. Investigating the mediating role of digital marketing and testing the 11th and 12th hypotheses

A- The mediating role of digital marketing in the relationship between competition intensity and financial performance

It was found that "intensity of competition" has an effect on "digital marketing" and "financial performance" and "digital marketing" is also effective on "financial performance". Therefore, to check the overall effect of competition intensity, the indirect effect of competition intensity should be taken into account.

The total effect of competition intensity on financial performance = direct effect of competition intensity + indirect effect of competition intensity

The direct effect of competition intensity on financial performance = 0.434

Indirect effect = the effect of the intensity of competition on financial performance × the effect of digital marketing on financial performance → $0.434 \times 0.427 = 0.185$

The total effect of competition intensity on financial performance = direct effect + indirect effect → $0.434 + 0.185 = 0.619$

Sobel statistics:

$$Z_1 = \frac{0.480 \times 0.478}{\sqrt{0.478^2 \cdot 0.07^2 + 0.656^2 \cdot 0.12^2}} = 2.750$$

The value of the test statistic using the Sobel test is greater than the value of 1.96. Therefore, it can be said that the mediating role of digital marketing variable is accepted. And in this way, it can be said with a probability of 95% that the adoption of digital marketing can mediate the effect of the intensity of competition on financial performance, and in this way, the eleventh hypothesis is confirmed.

B- The mediating role of digital marketing in the relationship between the intensity of commercial competition and non-financial performance

The direct effect of commercial competition intensity on non-financial performance = 0.449

Indirect effect = the effect of the intensity of commercial competition and non-financial performance
 × the effect of digital marketing on non-financial performance → $0.449 \times 0.478 = 0.214$

The total effect of commercial competition intensity on non-financial performance = direct effect +
 indirect effect → $0.449 + 0.214 = 0.663$

Sobel test:

$$Z_1 = \frac{0.480 \times 0.449}{\sqrt{0.449^2 \cdot 0.08^2 + 0.656^2 \cdot 0.12^2}} = 2.529$$

The value of the test statistic using the Sobel test is greater than the value of 1.96. Therefore, it can be said that the mediating role of digital marketing variable is accepted. And in this way, it can be said with a probability of 95% that the adoption of digital marketing can mediate the effect of competition intensity on non-financial performance. Thus, the twelfth hypothesis is also confirmed.

Assessment of model fit

In this research, structural model fitting using coefficient of determination index (R^2), index (Q^2) and GOF index has been used.

Coefficient of determination (R^2)

The coefficient of determination (R^2) is a measure that expresses the amount of changes in each of the dependent variables of the model, which is explained by the independent variables. The value of determination coefficient (R^2) is shown in table number 13.

Table 13: Coefficient of determination of endogenous structures of the model

Research variables	R^2
Digital marketing	0/714
Intensity of commercial competition	0/314
Financial performance	0/789
Non-financial performance	0/848

Source: research findings

Based on the results of the above table, the determination coefficient of the endogenous structures of the research model is favorable. The coefficient of determination of digital marketing is 0.848, business competition intensity is 0.314, financial performance is 0.789, and non-financial performance is 0.848, which is an acceptable value.

Conclusion

This research has been conducted with the aim of investigating digital marketing in mediating the effect of the Covid-19 epidemic and the intensity of competition on business performance. The first hypothesis showed that the presence of the Covid-19 epidemic had a significant effect on the commercial performance of online businesses in Iran. Businesses in general have a hard time sustaining themselves, especially if they want to improve their performance. One of the businesses that is under threat due to the covid-19 pandemic is online business trading. Online businesses are generally experiencing a decline in performance. The findings of Kokani et al. (9) are in line with the results of this research. The results of the second hypothesis showed that in today's era, due to the limitations of financial criteria and the special conditions of the knowledge age, the use of non-financial criteria is also unavoidable. Therefore, in addition to financial criteria, it is necessary to include non-financial criteria such as customer and employee satisfaction, innovation and quality, and the balanced evaluation card is a tool that realizes this importance. The findings of Kotler et al. (10) are in line with the results obtained in this research. The third hypothesis showed that in the era of Covid-19, businesses should reevaluate all policies and policies of the organization at the strategic level of the organization, look for new products and channels, adopt new approaches to customer

service, and use a new method of using Take advantage of opportunities to develop new markets using existing resources. The findings of Jiang et al. (11) are consistent with the results obtained in this study. The fourth hypothesis showed that, in general, competition in the product market has been proposed as a mechanism for corporate governance and an important and vital factor in making information disclosure decisions by companies, and as a component affecting the value of companies' shares, it also plays a role in this context, one of the factors It is important to obtain the confidence of investors and creditors for the optimal allocation of capital and to carry out profitable economic activities, to prepare and present information that is useful in making financial and economic decisions; In fact, in the era of Corona, in order to create an efficient capital market, it is necessary to have mechanisms to provide high-quality and accurate information. The findings of Amoha et al. (4) are consistent with the results obtained in this study. The fifth hypothesis showed that today the drivers of success in many industries are intangible assets such as intellectual capital and customer loyalty instead of physical assets included in the balance sheet. While it is difficult to measure and reflect intangible assets in the form of financial criteria, it is possible to provide non-financial data related to these assets. Kiskin et al., (12) is consistent with the results obtained in this study.

The sixth hypothesis showed that today's world is much different than companies must compete with other companies in order to survive in such a hyper-competitive market. Accordingly, they should have a smarter look at digital marketing and take advantage of it because the rapid development of technology has led to the creation of the digital age and digital activities are becoming the most important part of the marketing process.

The seventh hypothesis stated that people's access to the Internet and its growing trend, marketing is also affected. Marketing has always been about communicating with audiences at the right place and time, and that means companies need to target people where they're spending their time; That is, on the Internet. Therefore, offline marketing is no longer as effective as it used to be, and businesses must rush to digital marketing with a new approach to achieve high financial performance. The findings of Hinnings et al., (13) are in line with the results obtained in this study.

In the eighth hypothesis, it was found that the central value in market orientation is to prepare the organization to deal with new business conditions and to be able to obtain the necessary information from the market and prepare itself to respond to the market's needs. The findings of Newman et al. (14) are consistent with the results obtained in this study.

Examining the mediating role of digital marketing and testing the 9th and 10th hypotheses

A- The mediating role of digital marketing in the relationship between perception of the covid-19 pandemic on financial performance

It was found that "understanding of the Covid-19 pandemic" has an effect on "financial performance" and "digital marketing", and "digital marketing" is also effective on "financial performance". Therefore, to examine the overall impact of the perception of the Covid-19 epidemic on financial performance, the indirect effect of the perception of the Covid-19 epidemic should also be taken into account.

B- The mediating role of digital marketing in the relationship between the perception of the covid-19 pandemic and non-financial performance

It was stated that the adoption of digital marketing can mediate the effect of the Covid-19 pandemic on non-financial performance, and in this way, the tenth hypothesis is also confirmed. Now many people are turning to online businesses. The business of online businesses is still attractive because of their perception that everyone should fulfill their basic needs in the form of providing quality services. Even though the intensity of competition is getting tougher, businessmen should be able to prepare emergency strategies to deal with the crisis caused by the Covid-19 pandemic.

Investigating the mediating role of digital marketing and testing the 11th and 12th hypothesis

A- The mediating role of digital marketing in the relationship between competition intensity and financial performance

It was stated that the adoption of digital marketing can mediate the effect of the intensity of competition on financial performance and thus the eleventh hypothesis is confirmed. For many organizations, moving in Technology means to overtake the competitors and the business has a useful share of the market. It should be noted that today's customers are searching and obtaining purchase information online and businesses should move towards more efficient methods instead of using traditional and expensive methods. The use of traditional marketing methods generally have high costs, and in addition, the effectiveness of these advertisements is very low due to their lack of targeting.

B- The mediating role of digital marketing in the relationship between the intensity of commercial competition and non-financial performance

It stated that the adoption of digital marketing can mediate the effect of the intensity of competition on non-financial performance, and in this way, the twelfth hypothesis is also confirmed. The rapid change in the business environment in today's world has forced organizations to design their strategies and structure in order to respond to customer demand in a way that they can deal with these changes; therefore, it is inevitable to pay attention to human resources; because the ability of human resources makes organizations successful in achieving their goals. The findings of Amhoa et al. (4) are consistent with the results obtained in this study.

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